

High-Precision Kinematic Viscosity Measurement for Industrial Petroleum Products

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INTRODUCTION

Accurate viscosity measurement is essential for evaluating the quality and suitability of petroleum products in industrial applications. Viscosity—the resistance of a fluid to flow—can be thought of as its thickness, with higher viscosity indicating a thicker, slower-moving liquid. ASTM D445 and D446 provide detailed procedures for viscosity testing, including specifications for capillary viscometers and the temperature-controlled testing environment. Koehler's K23900 Kinematic Viscosity Bath meets these standards, delivering precise temperature control and real-time monitoring with an active thermometer.

ASTM D445 SIGNIFICANCE & ITS APPLICATIONS

ASTM D445 specifies the procedure for measuring the kinematic viscosity of liquids exhibiting Newtonian flow, defined by a fluid having a direct proportionality between its shear stress and rate of shear strain, which results in a constant viscosity regardless of applied force. This method covers a viscosity range from 0.02 mm²/s to 300,000 mm²/s. Viscosity is critical in selecting and applying lubricants, as low-viscosity fluids like alcohol flow readily, while high-viscosity substances like toothpaste resist flow under the same stress. In the automotive industry, understanding viscosity ensures the correct choice of engine oil. ASTM D445 is therefore an essential tool for evaluating how a fluid's viscosity responds to varying conditions and for determining its most suitable application.

INSTRUMENTATION

Koehler Instrument Company's K23900 Kinematic Viscosity Bath is designed in full compliance with ASTM D445 for measuring the kinematic viscosity of liquid petroleum products. The stainless-steel bath accommodates up to seven capillary viscometers and features displays for both setpoint and actual bath temperatures, with selectable °C or °F scales. Its precision temperature control (± 0.01 °C) is maintained through microprocessor-based PID circuitry, ensuring exceptional stability and uniformity across the operating range. The dual-tank system automatically adjusts liquid levels when viscometers are added, preventing overflow and maintaining consistent bath depth. Safety features include redundant overtemperature protection and low liquid level cut-off circuitry. For operator convenience, the unit incorporates LED illumination, coinciding with a baffle to provide a background for maximized visibility.

Kinematic Viscometers

TEST PREPARATION

1. Set the desired bath temperature and allow bath to stabilize.
2. Place the viscometer into the viscometer holder.
3. Charge the viscometer with sample.
4. Load the charged viscometer into the port.
5. Allow the sample and viscometer to warm to temperature.
6. Use a timer to measure the rate of flow through the capillary tube.

CONCLUSION

Viscosity is one of oil's most important defining properties and is a key factor in determining its classification and application. As a primary indicator of in-service behavior, viscosity is strongly influenced by temperature, making a stable testing environment essential for accurate measurement. Koehler Instrument Company's K23900 Kinematic Viscosity Bath delivers precise readings in full compliance with ASTM D445, offering temperature resolution and accuracy of ± 0.01 °C—exceeding ASTM specifications. Its semi-automated operation ensures reliable results, enabling accurate classification and optimal service application of lubricating oils.

Viscometer Holders

REFERENCES

ASTM D445 "Standard Test Method for Kinematic Viscosity of Transparent and Opaque Liquids (and Calculation of Dynamic Viscosity)", ASTM International, West Conshohocken, PA, 2022, DOI:10.1520/D0445-21E02

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